

TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE USING MODERN METHOD

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Annotation: *Teaching English has become the main core of education not only in our country but also the whole world.*

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There are a few types of techniques we can find in teaching English but we are not sometimes aware of their roles or how they result. It would be a clever way if we analyze techniques' results beforehand and sort out them according to our classroom environment and classroom target.

Firstly, common technique which is mostly used by teachers is small conversation. Teachers ask their students some kinds of simple questions in the beginning of the English lesson such as: "What's the date today?" or "It is sunny day, isn't it?". It

seems as a boring beginning of traditional lesson but this small conversation or dialogue plays a very essential role to improve learner's speaking skills as a basic step. The Change in their grades means development in their speaking because educators continue using difficult phrases or collocations according to their level. Secondly, we frequently face the acronym SWOT includes strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. We can load a bit hard task on learner's shoulder as he should write down his strong and weak points as well as opportunities and threats that he has during the learning process of the language. This helps the learner to use his positive sides and to try to overcome negative sides by working on himself. However, they can learn to make up a text by using these key points. They get them and put into writing or give a speech. It is a long-term process but its result is worthy to cope with. Every country owns their own pronunciation and this puts a barrier in pronouncing English words like a native person. Due to consonants, vowels and diphthongs which are different from our alphabet most learners find pronunciation difficult. The most effective techniques are listening to native speakers and telling tongue-twisters. By listening native speakers, they get accustomed to English pronunciation unconsciously. This results in improving speaking correctly without much effort. As it comes to telling tongue-twisters, it seems a bit funny for adults but by this way they learn how to pronounce words together as a native speaker.

Listening famous celebrities' speeches are considered not only useful but interesting and motivating. Before playing the audio, students are asked to write down important points of speech. At that time, they pay a great attention to the audio. It seems out of classroom environment but any piece of material which is in English helps learners to learn. This is the best way to improve listening for future studies and to get motivation to learn. Peer learning has some advantages and disadvantages over group learning. Firstly, we can share a lot of information with our partner during the time we spend with group. However, we can not collect various ideas to broaden our horizon. As it is seen, peer work is only useful for receptive skills if we use it in a wisely way. For example: teachers are able to tell them to make up dialogues or make a role play about any kind of topic. Learners use their overall knowledge and creativity. Some successful teachers in our country used peer learning to develop the English language because of the lack of students. To improve listening watching movies or videos plays the same vital role as listening audios plays. It is advisable for beginner and elementary students to watch videos or movies with subtitles. As a result, pronunciation of unfamiliar words becomes familiar and by the act or movement of the individuals in movies students can learn predictable meaning of new words. Most professional educators find this technique really important according to outcomes which are taken from them. Sometimes teachers use this unusual technique named "find similarities and differences". To conclude, we can find various techniques or methods to organize

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our lesson more interesting and efficiently, however, the most important thing is using them in their own place. In today's world every educator or teacher is advised to possess these techniques to catch up with educational advantages.

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